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Cop 29. Climate-Human Problem in the Context of the Philosophy of Life

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Abstract: *In our article "CLIMATE-HUMAN Problem in the Context of the Philosophy of Life", the most global problem faced by the states of the world in the modern era - the regressive effect of CLIMATE changes on the philosophy of life - is analyzed in the experience of the COP organized in a number of powerful countries of the world with the support of the United Nations and evaluated with scientific and logical conclusions.*

The author of the article tries to justify the importance of the COP 29 events, which will be held on November 11-24 of this year in the Republic of Azerbaijan, which renews the history of the COP, with full facts and sources, while analyzing the ways to escape from the global problem of climate change, which is the inevitable disaster of the world, and succeeds in this.

Key words: *United Nations Organization, Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, COP 29, philosophy of life.*

Introduction

It is natural that the life of Man, who is the supreme being of nature and the world, is the main issue of philosophy, especially its field of Life philosophy. The state of Nature - Environment, of which Man is a part, determines the life of Man and makes him think as the most important problem of the philosophy of Life.

From this point of view, United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), which entered into force on March 21, 1994, considers large-scale measures to solve problems important to human life.

Since 1995, events supporting the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) have been started in Berlin, Germany. Since then, 198 countries of the world have joined the Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP) and implemented a maximum action program to save the world.

The world community is already on the eve of the Framework Convention on Climate Change - COP 29, which will be held in the Republic of Azerbaijan on November 11-24, 2024. The reduction of water reserves, the expansion of greenhouses, the pollution of the air by factories caused by the natural needs of people, the emergence and spread of many diseases as a result of mass wars, the increase of global ecological problems year by year, even faster, the increase of human deaths all over the world, the importance of the Framework Convention on Climate Change highlights. Thus, these global events related to human health call the peoples of the world to unite for a Green World.

The Main part

The 29th session of the Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, known as COP29, is held in the Republic of Azerbaijan, which hosts large-scale international events with the aim of solving human issues such as Peace, Solidarity, Dialogue, Multiculturalism, Tolerance, and Cooperation. It is a prospective event.

One of the reasons justifying the holding of the COP-29 International event in the Republic of Azerbaijan is the solution of energy issues arising from the fact that Azerbaijan is an oil country with an ancient history, as well as the ecological recovery of the Nagorno-Karabakh territory, which has been occupied for 30 years and whose flora and fauna have been destroyed.

It should be noted that the selection of the host of the next climate conference, which was evaluated in two weeks, was accompanied by some disagreements. The fact is that the location of the COP is determined in turn by the five regional groups of the UN. As mentioned above, each regional group must unanimously decide on the nomination of a country from among its members to host the conference. In 2024, one of the Eastern European countries was planning to host the summit as part of the rotation. It is the Eastern European Regional Group's turn to host COP29 in 2024. However, the parties could not agree on a solution. Azerbaijan, which is included in this group, has put forward its candidacy to host the conference. Along with Azerbaijan, Armenia and Bulgaria also put forward their candidacy. But then Armenia, followed by Bulgaria, gave up their candidacy in favor of Azerbaijan.

Thus, on December 9, the Eastern European Regional Group designated Azerbaijan as the host country for the COP in 2020he

Now the President of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev, a committee consisting of 29 men and 12 women is working. In addition, 2024 has been declared the "Year of Solidarity for a Green World" in Azerbaijan. Nature, which is an inseparable part of man, is very important in relation to nature.

Thus the entire Republic of Azerbaijan is preparing for the COP29 national ceremony to be held in our country on November 11-24, 2024. We can say with certainty that in the present era, when the IV industrial revolution is taking place, calculated for the order of the world, as well as peaceful and tolerant Azerbaijan COP29 summit will be memorable and very important for the world and humanity.

It is also necessary to note that the activities of scientific institutions within the preparatory measures for the 29th session of the Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change, which will be held in our country, are significantly high.

For example, Agil Ahmadov, head of the "Image processing" group of "Azerkosmos" OJSC GIS (Geographic Information System) Center, and Elman Alasgarov, the center's product development specialist, provided information on the possibilities and solutions offered by this institution in various fields of the economy based on the database of satellite images of different areas and periods. Presented the results of the completed projects on the topics of "space monitoring of the effects of global climate changes on the Republic of Azerbaijan" and "identification of high-risk areas with a high probability of earthquakes in the country" (3).

Organization of monitoring of Earth's gravity and magnetic fields using open satellite data, comparison of satellite and field research results of geological faults and gravity anomalies, ways of integrated study of earthquake frequency and amplitude change and forms of cooperation in this field, as well as dynamics of climate changes in Azerbaijan, mineral deposits use of satellite data in detection, monitoring and prediction of eruptions of mud volcanoes, etc. issues are among modern topics.

On December 25, 2023, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, issued a Decree on the declaration of 2024 as the "Year of Solidarity for the Green World" in the Republic of Azerbaijan, and based on this Decree, it was decided to hold COP 29 events in the country on 11-24(1).

In the Order signed by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Aliyev, it is said about the essence and necessity of the COP 29 events: "The Republic of Azerbaijan contributes to the fight against the consequences of climate change as a reliable and responsible member of the international community. One of the five national priorities for socio-economic development of Azerbaijan until 2030 is defined as "Country of clean environment and green growth". In accordance with that priority, work is being done to improve the environment, restore and increase greenery, and ensure efficient use of water resources and sustainable energy sources. Compared to the base year (1990), Azerbaijan has set a goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 35 percent by 2030, and by 40 percent by 2050. Freed from occupation, Karabakh and East Zangezur, as well as the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, have been declared green energy zones. Environmental protection is a priority in the large-scale restoration and reconstruction process in liberated areas. In those areas, innovative approaches such as "smart city" and "smart village" are applied, and the ecosystem is restored(1).

In this order of historical importance, the main priority of the economic policy of the State of Azerbaijan, which confirms the real service to the goals of saving the world, is the issue of green energy. Azerbaijan aims to increase the share of renewable energy sources in the installed capacity of electricity production to 30 percent by 2030. The 29th session of the Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change - the unanimous decision to hold such a prestigious event as COP29 in Azerbaijan is a sign of great respect and trust for Azerbaijan by the international community, as well as for our country's national, regional and global environmental protection, climate is a clear example of the appreciation of his contribution to the prevention of changes"(1).

It has been almost a year since 2024 has been declared the year of "Solidarity for the Green World" and serious preparatory work has been carried out in various directions, especially in the fields of medicine and ecology.

For example, the strategic round table event held by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan within the framework of the 77th session of the World Health Assembly on "Climate change and health: a global vision for joint action" is important in this regard.

At this event, the Minister of Health of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Teymur Musayev, noted that "over the past decades, the intensification of extreme weather events such as floods, droughts and hurricanes, these climate events have an indirect effect on air and water pollution and land use possibilities, the number of diseases related to extreme heat continues to increase, and the number of diseases caused by heat. He noted that climate change causes many diseases that spread among people, transmission of infectious diseases.

Minister of Health Teymur Musayev regretfully emphasized that "It is proposed to include the subject "Climate change and health" in educational programs. In addition, the WHO Academy can play a key role in creating an online platform to provide continuing education on climate change and health. In addition, it is important for public health professionals to disseminate information to communities about the effects of climate change on physical and mental health¹".

The result

AIR-WATER-FOOD, changes in GLOBAL CLIMATE around the world - eg earthquakes, floods, volcanoes etc. by various names. it is natural that it includes a person, his consciousness, behavior, lifestyle, and the whole philosophy of life.

Thus, a HUMAN should think about everything for the sake of the world, from unhealthy foods, including smoking, to social and moral essence. As the environment surrounds him, he must be sensitive to its cleanliness. Man should plan his needs without plants and factories that produce life-threatening products. If a person takes into account how the products of cigarette production harm the air and his body at the same time, he will give up smoking. If a person understands how the destruction of countless old trees for the purpose of building high-rise buildings has a heavy impact on nature and climate, he will kill the interest of living in skyscrapers. Of course, thousands of examples can be given that it is the Man himself who goes against the philosophy of life and everything happens by his will. Even under the influence of some world politicians who are human, chemical products (weapons) factories are created, their waste poisons human life along with nature.

In this regard, it is very natural for the United Nations to sound the alarm and for leading countries to respond to it and hold COP events.

We believe that the joining of the Republic of Azerbaijan to the historically important COP program and the holding of COP29 events in Baku, the capital of Azerbaijan on November 11-24 of this year will help to achieve important results for the content and essentially the philosophy of life that billions of people expect from the CLIMATE CHANGE convention.

It should also be noted that world scientists will be widely represented at COP 29. We hope that both Azerbaijani scientific opinion and COP 29 designers will come up with ideas that will benefit the progress of every inhabitant of the Planet who came to the world once in the dialogue.

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